

Present Status and Trade Opportunities of Large Cardamom in Nepal

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Abstract: Large Cardamom (*Amomum Subulatum*) is a high value crop of Nepal, contributing to 13 percent of its export value. About 95 percent of the domestic produce of large cardamom is exported to India. This study, conducted during 2023-2024, engaged stakeholders through workshops, conferences, and comprehensive reviews of Nepalese large cardamom production and trade dynamics. Currently heavily reliant on the Indian market, Nepalese farmers face significant price volatility and limited bargaining power. Key barriers include high tariffs, regional trade dynamics, inadequate market research, weak policies, and regulatory gaps. To address these issues, the study recommends strategic actions such as trademark registration in export markets, comprehensive market feasibility studies in Middle Eastern countries, adoption of quality standards (GAPs and GMPs), intensified promotional efforts, and bilateral negotiations for trade facilitation. Implementing these strategies aims to diversify export destinations, improve product quality, and strengthen market presence, ultimately fostering sustainable growth in Nepal's large cardamom sub-sector.

Keywords: Large Cardamom, Trade, Nepal.

1. Introduction

Large Cardamom (*Amomum subulatum*) is a perennial herbaceous plant of family Zingiberace, very popular in the world as Black Cardamom, Black Gold and Queen of Spices. In Nepal, it is mostly cultivated in Eastern Nepal mostly concentrated in Taplejung, Sankhuwasabha and Panchthar district (MoALD, 2020). Among sixteen varieties of cardamom available in world, five types of cardamom cultivated in Nepal includes: Ramsey, Golsey, Sawney, Chibsey, and Dammersey (Kattel et al., 2020). It is also one of the high value crops having highest export value in terms of foreign currency earning (Sharma et al., 2016). According to MoALD (2020), large cardamom contributes 13% of the total country export value.

Studies shows that the produced cardamom are collected by traders at village level, district level, road head traders and ultimately to Birtamod traders. From Birtamod, only 10% is consumed in domestic market while 90% of the cardamom is exported to India (Kattel et al., 2020). While only a minor share of cardamom exported to Bangladesh, Pakistan and the UAE directly through Nepali traders. Indian traders imports the cardamom and re-export it to other countries like Pakistan and Bangladesh thus making a considerable benefits (Acharya et al., 2020; Kattel et al., 2020). This has created a market dependency

of Nepalese traders on Indian market for large cardamom export due to which Nepalese traders has to face various problems like low pricing, low bargaining power, etc (Acharya et al., 2020). So, with an aim to reach higher value niche market, in 2014, Trade and Export Promotion Centre (TEPC), in collaboration with the Federation of Large Cardamom Entrepreneurs of Nepal (FLCEN) and other major trading groups, established a collective trademark for large cardamom named 'Everest Big Cardamom' and registered it with the Department of Industry. This collective trademark was meant to be registered in international markets such as India, Bangladesh and Dubai. However, it has not registered in any countries except in Pakistan and the trademark has not been able to create the expected change in cardamom export (Acharya et al., 2020).

In this context, this paper assesses the present situation, bottlenecks, opportunities and national/international trade policies related to large cardamom and recommend a way forward related to issues and opportunities of international trade of large cardamom.

2. Methodology

Both qualitative and quantitative information were gathered and analyzed to assess the present status and trade opportunities of Nepalese large cardamom. Primary information was collected via inception meeting with *Sahaj* team at Biratnagar, Ministry of Agriculture, Koshi Province and Federation of Large Cardamom Association Nepal (FLAN) at Birtamod, Jhapa. Key informant interview (KII) was conducted to large cardamom collectors and exporters to assess present status, bottlenecks, and opportunities, and national/international trade policies related to large cardamom. Kick up workshop with concerned stakeholders in Koshi Province and Kathmandu in 2023-2024 and about more than 70 policy makers, government authorities, traders, input suppliers, associations and media were actively participated including 14 Provincial Assembly Members representing cardamom growing districts of Koshi Province and Secretary from Ministry of Industry, Agriculture and Cooperative (MoIAC), Government of the Koshi Province to explore and inform various opportunities and challenges in large cardamom trade (international trade). The provincial level workshop was organized by FLCEN in collaboration with *Sajah*-NAMDP Phase II. In addition, secondary information

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related to large cardamom present status, opportunities and challenges related to production and trade were reviewed from various published materials from MoALD, policies documents, Agriculture Development Strategy (ADS) and Provincial-ADS, Koshi Province.

3. Results and Discussion

A. Area, Production and Yield of Large Cardamom in Nepal

Table 1
Area, Production and Yield of Large Cardamom in Nepal and its 6 Provinces in Fiscal Year 2021/22

Nation/Province	Area (ha)	Production (Mt)	Yield (Mt/ha)
Nepal	15975	8714	0.54
Koshi Province	13904	7644	0.51
Bagmati Province	712	391	0.55
Gandaki Province	1054	541	0.51
Lumbini Province	204	74	0.36
Karnali Province	85	56	0.66
Sudurpaschim Province	16	8	0.55

Source: MoALD (2023)

Fig. 1. Percentage contribution of large cardamom in national production by province in Nepal

The Agriculture Development Strategy (2015-2035) has identified and prioritized large cardamom as the 5th sub-sector among fifteen identified sub-sectors for agribusiness development through the value chain approach in Nepal (MoAD, 2014). The area, production and productivity of large cardamom in Nepal was 15975 ha, 8714 MT and 0.54 MT/ha, respectively. The area, production and productivity of large cardamom was 13904 ha, 7644 MT and 0.51 MT/ha respectively in Koshi province. The area, production and productivity of Large Cardamom was 712 ha, 391 MT and 0.55 MT/ha, respectively in Bagmati province. The area, production and productivity of Large Cardamom was 1054 ha, 541 MT and 0.51 MT/ha, respectively in Gandaki province. The area, production and productivity of Large Cardamom was 712 ha, 391 MT and 0.55 MT/ha, respectively in Bagmati province. The area, production and productivity of Large Cardamom was 1054 ha, 541 MT and 0.51 MT/ha, respectively in Gandaki Province. The area production and productivity of Large Cardamom was 204 ha, 74 MT and 0.36 MT/ha respectively in Lumbini province. The area, production and productivity of Large Cardamom was 85 ha, 56 MT and 0.66 MT/ha respectively in Karnali Province. The area, production and

productivity of Large Cardamom was 16 ha, 8 MT and 0.50 MT/ha, respectively in Sudurpaschim Province (MoALD, 2023). Koshi Province contributes 87.8 percent followed by Gandaki Province (6.5%) and Bagmati Province (4.5%) to the national production in 2021/22.

Table 2
Production trend of large cardamom in Nepal

Year	Koshi (Mt)	Nepal (Mt)	% Cont. by Koshi
2005/06	6,505	6,646	97.88
2006/07	6,658	6,792	98.03
2007/08	6,931	7,087	97.80
2008/09	6,855	7,037	97.41
2009/10	5,010	5,232	95.75
2010/11	5,278	5,517	95.66
2011/12	5,640	6,026	93.59
2012/13	5,398	5,753	93.83
2013/14	4,906	5,225	93.90
2014/15	4,829	5,166	93.48
2015/16	6,064	6,439	94.18
2016/17	6,096	6,521	93.48
2017/18	6,106	6,849	89.15
2018/19	7,186	7,954	90.34
2019/20	8,673	9,545	90.86
2020/21	7,475	8,386	89.14
2021/22 (2078/79)	7,645	8,714	87.73

Fig. 2. Production trend of large cardamom in Koshi Province and Nepal within 16 years

B. Large Cardamom Area, Production and Yield in Koshi Province

Large cardamom is an economically important low volume high-value crop due to which, most of the farmers in Koshi province have shifted to the large cardamom cultivation. Compared to the traditional crops, the income from large cardamom is three to four times higher (SNV, 2010) The International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD, 2016) reported that, over 21960 households are engaged in large cardamom farming in Nepal. At present, Nepal is the largest producer of large cardamom with a 68 percent share in the global market, followed by India (22%) and Bhutan (9%). The area contribution of Large Cardamom in Koshi Province to the nation is 90.9%, where the contribution on national production is 90.8%. Large cardamom has been a prioritized crop by Nepal Trade Integration Strategy (NTIS) and Agriculture Development Strategy (ADS, 2015-2035). All the parameters of production status (area, production, and productivity) are found increasing in the national context supported by ITC (2017). In 2005/06 the area, production and

productivity of Large Cardamom in Nepal was 11498 ha, 6646 Mt and 0.578 Mt/ha, respectively whereas the area, production and productivity of ginger in Koshi province was 11238 ha, 6505 Mt and 0.579 Mt/ha, respectively. In 2020/21 potential districts of large cardamom production in Nepal are Taplejung, Panchther, Sankhuwasava, and Terathum districts.

area has been increased by 106.66 ha per year whereas production increased by 2.29 Mt/year. Koshi province contributes 87.04% total area and 87.73% production in the nation. Annual yield of large cardamom in Koshi Province has been decreased by 4.2 kg/ha on an average within 16 years (Figure 5).

Table 3
Area and production of large cardamom among Koshi province districts in 2021/22

District	Area (ha)	Production (Mt)
Taplejung	4,272	2,851
Sankhuwasava	2,128	968
Solukhumbu	150	110
Panchthar	3,164	1,476
Ilam	1,671	869
Terathum	611	292
Dhankuta	118	50
Bhojpur	599	360
Khotang	1,064	585
Okhaldhuna	31	21
Udhayapur	38	26
Jhapa	2	1
Morang	43	27
Sunsari	13	9
Total in Koshi	13,904	7,645
Total in Nepal	15975	8714

Source: MoALD (2023)

Fig. 5. Yield trend of large cardamom in Koshi province

Fig. 3. Yield of large cardamom in 14 districts of Koshi Province and Nepal

Fig. 4. Trends of area and production of large cardamom in Koshi province over 16 years

Figure 4 shows the positive trends of large cardamom area and production in Koshi province over 16 years. The productive

C. Expert Scenario, Market Standard and Price of Large Cardamom in Nepal

The export price was found lower than the prevailing rate of large cardamom in Birtamod market. Exporters have to prepare lower invoices according to advice of transporter and the importing party to avoid 4.5% state movement tax to be paid in value of consignment. (ITC, 2017; Joshi & Piya, 2019). There is also a malpractice of mixing Nepalese produce with cheap import from China and Guatemala (ITC, 2017). Annual export quantity of large cardamom from Nepal has been increased by 28.36 MT per hectare (Figure 6).

Birtamod to Karachi via road through Wagah-3000 km, Birtamod to Karachi via sea through Kolkata-5000 km, India does not allow Nepalese to export through Wagah. (Acharya, et al., 2020). Bangladesh which is the major market of Bhutanese large cardamom has substantially waived tariffs for Bhutanese imports whereas the customs tariff for Nepalese cardamom is more than 54 percent. (ITC, 2017). India has waived all types of tax on the movement of Bhutanese products through territory of India whereas Nepalese counterparts should pay 4.5% state movement tax on value. (ITC, 2017). Due to such ad valorem tax, Nepalese traders should have to prepare low invoices to reduce tax which reduces the insurance amount. (ITC, 2017).

India exports less than what it imports. India is the world's largest consumer of spices and thus India itself is the major market for Nepalese cardamom. Afghanistan, Pakistan, UAE, UK and USA respectively are the top importers of large cardamom from India in year 2019/20 with Afghanistan importing large cardamom from India. However, the import value of Pakistan is higher than Afghanistan (Indian Spices Board, 2020). The demand for cardamom in Middle East countries is mainly of green cardamom (MoAF, 2017). The export quality and value of large cardamom is highly fluctuated and in declining trend and about more than 95% Nepalese large cardamom is being exported in India. In fiscal year 2022, total export quantity of large cardamom is 9931 Mt with monetary

value of NRs. 8 Arab 24 crore and fifteen lakhs (8241.5 million NRs.) which was about 50% lower value in 2021 (NRs. 4764.38 million). Due to high stock holding the export volume in 2022 was higher than national production fetching good price (NRs. 850- 1875/kg) as compared to previous years (NRs. 625-1000/kg) (refer Table 4).

Table 4
Trend of large cardamom export volume and value from Nepal

Year	Exported Quantity (Mt.)	Export Value (NRs.)
2012	5523	3,632,474,412
2013	5321	2,319,134,045
2014	3523	3,254,166,036
2015	3217	4,717,223,752
2016	3006	3,888,374,024
2017	4656	4,503,910,808
2018	4329	3,826,983,423
2019	3358	2,718,022,124
2020	8566	6,895,422,480
2021	5280	4,764,389,360
2022	9931	8,241,513,469

Sources: TEPC (Official Website); FLCEN data source

Fig. 6. Trends of quantity of large cardamom export from Nepal

Fig. 7. Trends of exported value of large cardamom from Nepal

In Nepal, quality of large cardamom is determined through the process of ‘Grading. Basically, it is a locally based process where products are segregating into three types such as Jumbo Jet (JJ), Standard type/super deluxe (SD) and usual type which

locally called *Chalan Chalti* (CC). This segregation is made on the base of its Size, Colour and tail cutting (ITC, 2017). Following Table 5 shows the various quality measurements in large cardamom.

Fig. 8. Price of large cardamom in Birtamod, Jhapa based on grades in 1 December 2023 (Source: FLCEN (1st Dec. 2023); 1 man = 40 kg)

D. Stakeholders Analysis of Large Cardamom in Nepal

The different stakeholders involved in large cardamom are: Governmental bodies like Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock Development (MoALD), Ministry of Industry, Commerce and supplies (MoICS), Department of agriculture (DOA), Department of Food Technology and Quality Control (DFTQC), Trade and Export Promotion Centre (TEPC), Ministry of Finance (MoF)/Department of Custom (DOC), Prime Minister Agriculture Modernization Project (PMAMP: Super Zone and Zone), Ministry of Land Management, Agriculture and Cooperative (MoLMAC)/MoIAC at Provincial level, Agriculture Knowledge Center (Block & Pocket programs), Cardamom Development Center (CDC) Plant Protection Directorate (PPD), Plant Quarantine Office, Customs Office, Commercial Crop Division (CCD), National Spice Crop Development Program (NSCDP), Municipalities, Rural Municipalities, Agriculture Inputs Corporation (AIC) and Spice crop development sectors of Nepal Agricultural Research Council (NARC), Provincial Government as well as development partners (Sahaj, ICIMOD, Trade and Competitiveness Project/USAID, etc.). Mostly of the activities of these institutions are concentrated on production side with very few investments in research related to Large Cardamom. While non-government institutions working in Large Cardamom sub-sector are International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD), UNNATI Inclusive growth project, International Trade Centre (ITC), Asia Network for Sustainable Agriculture and Bio-resources (ANSAB), Agricultural cooperatives, Saving and Credit Cooperatives, Private sectors like Federation of Large Cardamom

Table 5
Grade and specification of large cardamom in Nepal

Grade and specification	Jumbo jet (JJ)	Standard /Super Delux (SD)	Chalanchalti/Ilami (CC)
Hygiene	Free of dust, smoke, and fungus		
Size	Large (>14 mm)	Large (>14 mm)	Small (<10 mm)
Tail cut	Yes	Yes	<15% tail/Absent
Color	Natural (Brownish to Pinkish)	Natural (Brownish to Pinkish)	Natural
Moisture	<12%	<12%	>12%
Medium-sized	<5%	<10%	

Table 6
Stakeholders, category, objectives and major roles for large cardamom trade promotion in Nepal

Stakeholders	Category	Objectives	Major roles/Activities
MoALD at federal level MoIAC at Provincial level	Government	Develop national /provincial cardamom policy and institutional mechanism for sector coordination	Formulate national cardamom policy, action plan to support export strategy, increase financial support to R&D, branding and product development
MoCIS	Government	Improve commercial diplomacy	Support visits from governmental and private sectors
TEPC	Government	Develop export quality standard and new collective trademark	Adopt collective trademark for Black and Pink cardamom, benchmark analysis
DFTQC	Government	Improve certification services in MRL testing	International accreditation recognition of certified laboratories
		Develop export quality standard and new collective trademark	Adopt collective trademark for Black and Pink cardamom, benchmark analysis
Cardamom Development Centre (CDC)	Government	Ensure quality and disease-free seedlings for farmers	Support for development of private nurseries and disease-free certification schemes, extensive training for quality farming, disease minimization
Agriculture Knowledge Centre (AKC), Agriculture Division of Palikas	Government	Improve productivity of Orchards	Training of farmers and technicians, establishment of model orchards in each district, awareness campaign, irrigation system
		Develop and disseminate modern dryers, establishment of storage facility	Agriculture Knowledge Centre, Agriculture Division of Palikas
FLCEN	Association/Private	Adopt compulsory export quality standards	Dissemination of grading system of FLCEN to farmers, moisture, physical and chemical characteristics assessment, benchmark analysis of competing cardamom, trace MRL
		Develop exporter’s capacities	Improve knowledge about international business practices, develop new direct sales channel in traditional importing markets, investigation of air freight, cardamom sales outlet in major markets, product development and differentiation
Agriculture and Forestry University, Other Universities in Nepal	Technical Government University	Teaching, Research and Extension	Research on diseases management, value chain analysis, production efficiency and international trade promotion, Climate resilience large cardamom farming teaching and extension

Table 7
Stakeholders involve large cardamom sub-sector in Nepal

Territory	Governmental	Non-governmental	Private sector
Central	MoALD, MoICS, DoA, DFTQC), TEPC, MoF/DoC, AKC, CDC, PPD, CCD, NSCDP, AIC, AEC and Spice crop development sectors of NARC, PMAMP	ICIMOD, UNNATI, ITC, ANSAB, Swisscontact/NAMDP Phase II, Mercy Corps	FNCCI, FLCEN
Province	Provincial government, Ministry of Land Management Agriculture and Cooperative (MoLMAC)/Agriculture, DoA, PMAMP	NAMDP Phase II	FNCCI, FLCEN
District/regional	Agriculture Knowledge Centre (AKC), Customs Office, Plant Quarantine Office	NGOs, COs	FLCEN, CCI
Local	Rural Municipality, Municipality (Palikas)	Agricultural cooperatives, Agro-vets, farmers cooperatives etc.	Micro-financial institutions, credit cooperatives, savings, Farmers

Entrepreneurs of Nepal (FLCEN), Federation of Chamber of Commerce and Industry (FNCCI), nursery growers, individuals (local traders), Agro-vets, infrastructures, rules, policy and Pocket package system and Mercy Corps. The above description can be put into the following Table 6.

E. International Trade of Nepalese Large Cardamom

Most of the cardamom produced in Nepal is collected in Birtamod. More than half of the trade volume was shipped to India's Siliguri, and the other half was shipped to Delhi and Kolkata. In the Eastern Himalayan region, particularly Nepal, India's Sikkim, and Bhutan, Siliguri is regarded the key regional hub for large cardamom. Nepalese large cardamom is being export to Pakistan and Middle East Countries via Dubai from Mumbai and major market hubs of India (Figure 9).

Fig. 9. Flow of Nepalese large cardamom in international market

The current monopoly of Indian traders, as well as the lack of direct contacts with ultimate purchasers, limit Nepali traders' capacity to react quickly. Prices are typically set by purchasers at the Delhi market, with following prices set by other traders at the central, wholesale, district, and village market centers.

Table 8
Status of Nepalese large cardamom in international markets: problems with possible solutions

Countries	Indian market of Nepalese cardamom	Other countries from India	Problems	Solutions
India	More than 90% export Places: Delhi, Mumbai, UP (Banaras, Kanpur, Tarkhan) Amritsahar Kalkata	Via Mumbai: Pakistan, Middle East Countries Via Bhutan: Bangladesh Delhi: via Dubai Pakistan Kalkata and Bishaka (AP) Port for Nepalese Large Cardamom - --export to other countries from India	Lack of own Testing Lab (Depend on Indian Lab in Kalkata and vehicle wait 5-6 days to take lab certificate) Long waiting period in Kalkata port shipping (45-60 days)	International standard valid lab requires in Nepal and G-G negotiation to Indian Government Facilitation for Mumbai port for large cardamom cargo shipping (Direct)
Bangladesh	Very few cardamom	Via Bhutan to Bangladesh (0% tariffs for Bhutan)	35% traffic for Nepalese and Indian large cardamom	G-G to negotiation for 35% tariffs down
Pakistan	About 45% Nepalese cardamom goes to Pakistan via Dubai through India	High Duty and Under value LC	Full LC requires from Pakistan. G-G negotiation required. Direct Trade Functional bilateral trade agreement (collective trademark)	Pakistan
Middle East Countries Other countries (EU, USA, Canada, etc.)	Via India to Dubai	Low demand (1-5 Mt) per buyer Delay delivery (45-60 days from Kalkata port) High transport cost (NRs. 50-80/kg in air cargo) (NRs. 20-30 /kg in shipping cargo)	Transport subsidy Via. Mumbai port for shipping (G-G negotiation with India) Certification (organic, Faire Trade, GI) GMP product	Middle East Countries Other countries (EU, USA, Canada, etc.)

Pricing for traders and farmers inside the country is dependent on the grading of large cardamom. Jumbo Jet (JJ), Standard (SD), and *Chalan Chalti* (CC) are the three distinct price categories for large cardamom. The pricing records per man (40 kg) that is currently available. In 2014/15, the average price at Ilam (Fikkal) for Jumbo Jet was US \$ 27.64 per kg, US \$ 25.13 per kg for Standard, and US \$ 24.62 per kg for *Chalan Chalti* (ITC, 2017).

The majority of prominent cardamom exporters have established relationships with Indian buyers. They have not yet developed the capacity to bear the risks of exporting cardamom directly to Pakistan or other Middle Eastern markets. Their risk-taking potential is limited, owing to a lack of understanding of Nepalese legislation, certification requirements, administrative procedures, and export documentation requirements. Nepali traders are limited to exporting to their typical Indian importers due to a lack of understanding about trade facilities and the documentation required (ITC, 2017).

Access to the market for Nepalese large cardamom in other countries is found low due to:

- Indian Customs Office doesn't recognize quarantine certificate by government lab of Nepal, total cost in certification in Kolkata costs 2 weeks and US\$ 300 per screening (Acharya et al., 2020).
- Increasing unfair competition: 'Duplicate' black cardamom¹ is transported to Pakistan by Indian traffickers combined with Nepali large cardamom in order to lower the price.
- Lack of suitable provisions and G-G coordination in bilateral agreements for market access to Pakistan and Bangladesh.
- Limited number of wholesalers and exporters in

Nepal.

- No access of Mumbai shipping port to export Nepalese large cardamom to other countries.
- Lack of transportation insurance services to export. There are only two transporters who can manage safe transportation of goods to Delhi (ITC, 2017).
- Limited governmental support at the sector level for trade development activities.
- Informal costs in route to Delhi comes around INR 25 per kg (ITC, 2017).

The trade in Nepalese large cardamom is monopolized by a small group of Delhi traders who keep Nepalese exporters in the dark about quality, pricing, business ties, and trends, and who retaliate harshly if Nepalese exporters pursue direct contacts with either India or Pakistan. The benefits of Pakistan's high prices primarily benefit Indian traders.

Imports of ('duplicate') black cardamom from new origins, in which the same Indian traders are involved, are threatening this long-standing economic model. This is a contradictory condition that will cause Nepalese large cardamom exports to stagnate. The main trade barriers that large cardamom exporters confront are issues with conformity evaluation and procedural barriers. The samples are sent to Kolkata, which is a long way from the Customs post, for testing. Obtaining the report and clearing the items through Customs takes more than 14 days. Even when test findings show no abnormalities, exporters complain that passing the shipment without making unofficial payments to Indian officials is tough (ITC, 2017). Detail status of Nepalese large cardamom trading in international markets, problems and possible solutions is presented in Table 8.

¹ Duplicate large cardamom is adulated with poor quality cardamom (size, color and grade) mentioned in ITC (2017). There is also a malpractice of mixing Nepali produce with cheap import from China and Guatemala (ITC, 2017).

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concluded that the high tariffs, long standing trade relation among Pakistan and India, lack of promotion and market study in potential market niches, weak government policy, lack of sanitary and phytosanitary measures are the hurdles for promotion of Nepalese large cardamom in export countries. Based on production and trade status of Nepalese large cardamom reviewed as well as issues raised during provincial and national large cardamom workshop, following recommendation are made for improvement of large cardamom trade in international market and issues need to be discussed during federal/national level cardamom workshop in Kathmandu:

- Bilateral trade negotiations through G2G approach mainly for unitization of Mumbai shipping port, lab certification report validity from Nepal to India, tariff (tax) free trade to Bangladesh.
- Intergovernmental negotiation to Pakistan and Bangladesh to reduce the tax of 35% in export should be done by Nepal government.
- Government to Government (G2G) bilateral agreement for promotion of Nepalese large cardamom under registration of collective trade should be made between India, Bangladesh and Gulf countries in collaboration with SAFTA and other regional trade alliance. The LC (Letter of Credit) should be fixed at the time of trade negotiation between exporter and importer under governments supervision.
- The following actions are required to promote Nepalese large cardamom in Pakistan: (i) A brand profile must be developed based on market research in Pakistan. The aim of this market research in Pakistan would be to determine if consumers are being cheated when they purchase large cardamom from Nepal which it is actually mixed with 'duplicate' black cardamom, (ii) In order to move away from the current monopoly of Indian traders, the sector needs to

collaborate to set up new trade routes to access Pakistan directly using Mumbai shipping port via G2G negotiation, and (iii) Look for new export market opportunities for Nepalese large cardamom linked to the Pakistani diaspora and Muslim countries.

- Need of national policy and establishment of Large Cardamom Board.
- Warehouse and warehouse receipt financing including insurance service.
- Explore and promotion of domestic markets including market assessment for product diversification and value addition.
- Trade diplomacy for export promotion.
- Research and development (R&D) related to disease control, irrigation scheme and orchard management for improving productivity of large cardamom.

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